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**TEACHING PROFESSIONALISM AMONG
MEDICAL TEACHERS: STUDENTS
PERSPECTIVE**

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ABSTRACT:

Professional development is learning to earn or maintain professional credentials such as academic degrees to formal coursework, attending conferences, and informal learning opportunities situated in practice. It has been described as intensive and collaborative, ideally incorporating an evaluative stage. This cross-sectional study was conducted among medical students at different medical colleges. All the students were given a predefined questionnaire. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. There were 90 medical students included in this study. The mean age of the students was 21.43 ± 1.78 years. There were 60 (66.67%) males and 30 (33.33%) females in this study. Out of 90 students, 40 told that the teachers had sound grip of the topics and that they were able to understand the topics with the current methodologies of teaching. Fifty students told that, teachers are not well prepared and that they only read the slides. None of the students responded negative remarks about of the behavior of teachers.

**KEYWORDS: TEACHING PROFESSIONALISM,
PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT**

INTRODUCTION:

Professional development is learning to earn or maintain professional credentials such as academic degrees to formal coursework, attending conferences, and informal learning opportunities situated in practice. It has been described as intensive and collaborative, ideally incorporating an evaluative stage. There is a variety of approaches to professional development, including consultation, coaching, communities of practice, lesson study, mentoring, reflective supervision and technical assistance. There are several challenges inherent in teaching professionalism. The first is to obtain agreement on a definition. The next is how best to impart knowledge of professionalism to students and faculty. Of great importance is how to encourage those behaviors characteristic of a professional (developing a professional identity). Traditionally professionalism was

taught by role-models. This is still an essential method but it is no longer sufficient. Both faculty, many of whom are role-models, and students should understand the nature of contemporary professionalism. In the literature there are two approaches to teaching professionalism; to teach it explicitly as a series of traits or as a moral endeavor, stressing reflection and experiential learning. Neither alone is sufficient. Teaching it by providing a definition and listing a series of traits gives students only a theoretical knowledge of the subject. Relying solely on role modeling and experiential learning is selective, often disorganized, and actually represents what was done in the past. Both approaches must be combined in order that students both understand the nature of professionalism and internalize its values.

The first step to be taken in teaching professionalism is to teach its

cognitive base explicitly. This will allow both faculty and students to have the same understanding of the nature of professionalism and share the same vocabulary as they reflect upon it. A medical institution should therefore select and agree on the definition of a profession and its attributes. There is some confusion in the literature on the exact nature of the words profession and professionalism, with some believing that it is difficult to define professionalism as it is too complex and context driven. There are however several definitions available, and all contain similar content. There are also attributes, drawn from the literature, which outline what is expected of a medical professional and these can form the basis of identifying the behaviors which reflect these attributes (1-3). The objective of this study is to determine the teaching professionalism among medical teachers in different medical colleges.

MATERIAL OF METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted among medical students at different medical colleges. All the students were given a predefined questionnaire. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. The quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation. The qualitative variables were presented as frequency and percentages.

RESULTS:

There were 90 medical students included in this study. The mean age of the students was 21.43 ± 1.78 years. There were 60 (66.67%) males and 30 (33.33%) females in this study. Out of 90 students, 40 told that the teachers had sound grip of the topics and that they were able to understand the topics with the current methodologies of teaching. Fifty students told that, teachers are not well prepared and that they only read the slides. None of the students

responded negative remarks about of the behavior of teachers.

DISCUSSION:

Initial professional development (IPD) is defined as "a period of development during which an individual acquires a level of competence necessary in order to operate as an autonomous professional". Professional associations may recognize the successful completion of IPD by the award of chartered or similar status. Examples of professional bodies that require IPD prior to the award of professional status are the Institute of Mathematics and its Applications, the Institution of Structural Engineers, and the Institution of Occupational Safety and Health. Continuing professional development (CPD) or continuing professional education (CPE) is continuing education to maintain knowledge and skills. Most professions have CPD obligations. Examples are the Royal Institution of Chartered Surveyors, American Academy of

Financial Management, safety professionals with the International Institute of Risk & Safety Management (IIRSM) or the Institution of Occupational Safety and Health (IOSH), and medical and legal professionals, who are subject to continuing medical education or continuing legal education requirements, which vary by jurisdiction. A systematic review published in 2019 by the Campbell Collaboration found little evidence of the effectiveness of continuing professional development (4-6).

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